

On Colloidal Electrolytes

Attempt to Account for the Variation of Osmotic Pressure of Polyacrylic Acid with its Progressive Neutralisation by NaOH and to Find its Dissociation constant

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

(Received 25 March 1972)

From a consideration of the equilibrium that exists between the counter ions adsorbed in the fixed Stern-Mukherjee layer and those present in the diffuse part of the electrical double layer of the particles of a polyacrylic acid sol the following equation has been deduced connecting the activity, a_s , of the counter ions in the diffuse layer with the concentration of the N^+ ions added in the form of NaOH

$$a_s = \frac{K_3 f}{K_4 S_x d} \cdot \frac{a_k}{K_0 + C_k}$$

The significance of the terms in the equation has been explained in the paper.

It has been pointed out that the activity of the counter ions in the diffuse double layer is manifested only when the particles of the PAA sol with their double layers come in contact with the osmometer membrane. Therefore, if θ be the fraction per unit area of the osmometer with which the double layers are in contact, then θa_s should represent the activity of the counter ions at the membrane per unit area and hence the osmotic pressure p is given by the equation

$$P = RT(\theta a_s) = TR\theta \frac{K_3 f}{S_x d K} \cdot \frac{a_k}{K_0 + C_k}$$

For a given value of θ , $RT\theta K_3 f / K_4 S_x d$ is constant and hence the aforesaid equation may be written as :

$$P = K \frac{a_k}{K_0 + C_k}$$

The equation has been found to agree well with the data recorded by Kern on the measurement of osmotic pressure of some PAA sols when they are being neutralised by NaOH.

The following equation connecting the "surface dissociation constant" K_s with the observed H^+ ion activity H_c has been deduced :

$$H_c = \theta K_s \frac{(1-\alpha)^n}{(\alpha)^n}$$

Using this equation the "surface dissociation constant" K_s of PAA has been calculated and found to be 1.1×10^{-5} or $P^{K_s} = 4.95$.

Kern¹ has determined the osmotic pressure, p , of polyacrylic acid (PAA) of average degree of polymerisation (p. 340), when it is being progressively neutralised by NaOH. Four

different concentrations of the acid have been investigated. For each concentration he has found that the plot of a_k/p against the relative concentration a_k of the cations is linear. He has, therefore, proposed the following empirical equation

$$p = \frac{a_k}{a \cdot a_k + b} \quad (1)$$

where p represents the osmotic pressure, a_k the ratio of the sum of the concentrations of Na^+ and H^+ ions to the number of gram equivalents* of PAA taken per litre and, a and b are constants.

It will be shown in this paper that an equation similar to that proposed by Kern¹ can be deduced from a consideration of the equilibrium that exists between the counter ions adsorbed in the fixed Stern²-Mukherjee³ layer and those present in the diffuse part of the electrical double layer surrounding each of the particles of the PAA sols.

Derivation of the equation for Osmotic Pressure : Consider an unit volume of a sol of PAA containing x particles,** each having the same surface area, S , and to this system C_{Na} equivalents of NaOH have been added. The NaOH will enter the diffuse double layer, the OH^- ions will neutralise the H^+ ions and the Na^+ ions will take the place of these H^+ ions. The equilibrium between the H^+ ions adsorbed in the fixed Stern-Mukherjee layer and those in the diffuse double layer will be disturbed and some of the adsorbed H^+ will pass from the fixed layer to the diffuse layer to restore equilibrium. A few Na^+ ions say, Y equivalents will be adsorbed in the fixed layer on some of the points vacated by the H^+ ions.

When equilibrium is attained, let C_H/Sxd and $(C_{Na} - Y)/Sxd$ represent the concentration of the H^+ and Na^+ ions respectively in the diffuse double layer of average thickness, d and let n represent the total number, covered and uncovered, of active points per unit area of the Stern-Mukherjee layer at the surface of the particles where adsorption of H^+ or Na^+ ions can occur.

At equilibrium the following relation should hold good for the exchange of the Na^+ ions between the fixed layer and the diffuse layer;

$$K_1 N \left(\frac{C_H + C_{Na} - Y}{Sxn} \right) (C_{Na} - Y)/Sxd = K_2 \left(\frac{Y}{Sxn} \right) N$$

where N represents the Avogadron Number, $N(C_H + C_{Na} - Y)/Sxn$ the fraction of the surface uncovered per unit area, $(C_{Na} - Y)/Sxd$ the concentration of the Na^+ ions in the diffuse double layer, YN/Sxn , the fraction of the surface covered by the Na^+ ions, per unit area and K_1 and K_2 are the velocity constants.

It follows from equation (2) that

$$(C_H + C_{Na} - Y) = K_3 \frac{Y}{(C_{Na} - Y)} \quad (3)$$

where $K_3 = Sxd K_2/K_1$.

* 72 grams have been taken as the equivalent weight of PAA by Kern.

** As in the previous paper⁴, it is assumed here also that $x = K(C_{gm} - C_0)$, where C_{gm} represents the concentration of PAA and C_0 its c.m.c. or solubility.

$$\text{or,} \quad \frac{C_H + C_{Na}}{Y} - 1 = \frac{K_3}{(C_{Na} - Y)} \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{or,} \quad Y = \frac{(C_{Na} - Y)(C_H + C_{Na})}{K_3 + (C_{Na} - Y)} \quad (3b)$$

Substituting this value of Y in equation (3) we get

$$(C_H + C_{Na} - Y) = \frac{K_3(C_H + C_{Na})}{K_3 + (C_{Na} - Y)} \quad (3c)$$

or,

$$(C_H + C_{Na} - Y)f/Sxd = \frac{K_3f(C_H + C_{Na})}{Sxd[K_3 + (C_{Na} - Y)]} \quad (3d)$$

where f represents the average activity coefficient.

The L.H.S. in equation (3d) represents the activity of the counter ions in the diffuse double layer and may be put equal to $a_s K_4$ where K_4 is a proportionality constant.

In a previous paper it has been shown by the author¹, that if θ be the fraction per unit area of the surface of the osmometer membrane with which the diffuse double layers of the colloidal particles are in contact and a_s , the activity of the counter ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact then the observed osmotic pressure p is given by the expression

$$P = RT\theta a_s \quad (4)$$

where $\theta = \frac{C_{gm}}{K + C_{gm}}$ in which K is a constant and C_{gm} represents the number of gram equivalents of PAA per litre of the sol.

Therefore, multiplying both the sides of the equation (3d) by $RT\theta$, we get the equation for the observed osmotic pressure

$$p = RT\theta(C_H + C_{Na} - Y)f/K_4 Sxd = (RT\theta K_3 f/K_4 Sxd) \frac{(C_H + C_{Na})}{K_3 + (C_{Na} - Y)} \quad (4a)$$

Multiplying both the numerator and the denominator of (4a) by C_{gm} and neglecting Y in the denominator which is small compared to $K_3 + C_{Na}$ we get

$$p = K \frac{a_k}{K_0 + C_k} \quad (5)$$

where $K = RT\theta K_3 f/K_4 Sxd$, $a_k = (C_H + C_{Na})/C_{gm}$, $K_0 = K_3/C_{gm}$ and $C_k = C_{Na}/C_{gm}$.

It may be mentioned that for a given value of C_{gm} , K and K_0 should remain constant and that $a_k \rightarrow C_k$ as $C_H \rightarrow 0$.

Equation (5) is thus similar to equation (1) proposed empirically by Keru.

Verification of the equation for osmotic pressure : In the following tables are recorded the data of Kern¹ on measurement of osmotic pressure of PAA (p. 340) as it is being neutralised by NaOH. As the initial values of C_H are somewhat uncertain (since different values

for the same system are found in different tables) we have recorded in the Tables 1 to 4 only those data for which $C_{Na} \gg C_H$.

TABLE 1

$C_{gm} = 0.01$		$K = 0.044$		$K_0 = 0.27$	
C_{Ng}	Activity of H^+ ions	C_k	a_k	$P_{obs} \times 10^3$ atmospheres	$P_{cat} \times 10^3$ atmospheres
0.001	3.09×10^{-5}	0.10	0.105	13.0	12.5
0.002	1.12×10^{-5}	0.20	0.201	19.2	18.8
0.004	—	0.40	0.400	27.7	26.3
0.006	—	0.60	0.600	29.5	30.4
0.008	—	0.80	0.800	32.5	32.9
0.01	—	1.00	1.000	33.3	34.6

TABLE 2

$C_{gm} = 0.0625$		$K = 0.32$		$K_0 = 0.287$	
C_{Na}	Activity of H^+ ions	C_k	a_k	$P_{obs} \times 10^3$ atmospheres	$P_n \times 10^3$ atmospheres
0.002	3.47×10^{-4}	0.032	0.038	38.7	38.4
0.004	1.45×10^{-4}	0.064	0.066	56.5	60.2
0.008	4.37×10^{-5}	0.128	0.130	104.9	101.1
0.016	7.42×10^{-6}	0.256	0.256	165.3	150.7
0.032	5.75×10^{-7}	0.512	0.512	208.1	205.1
0.040	1.95×10^{-7}	0.640	0.640	217.8	220.8
0.050	3.31×10^{-8}	0.80	0.80	239.2	235.5
0.060	—	0.96	0.96	241.0	246.4

TABLE 3

$C_{gm} = 0.125$		$K = 0.7$		$K_0 = 0.287$	
C_{Na}	Activity of H^+ ions	C_k	a_k	$P_{obs} \times 10^3$ atmospheres	$P_{cat} \times 10^3$ atmospheres
0.01	1.15×10^{-4}	0.080	0.081	156	155
0.02	3.09×10^{-5}	0.160	0.160	249	251
0.04	7.76×10^{-6}	0.320	0.320	385	369
0.06	1.41×10^{-6}	0.480	0.480	452	438
0.08	5.37×10^{-7}	0.640	0.640	475	483
0.10	7.42×10^{-8}	0.80	0.80	514	515
0.12	—	0.96	0.96	537	539

TABLE 4

$C_{Na} = 0.25$		$K = 1.52$		$K_0 = 0.287$	
C_{Na}	Activity of H^+ ions	C_k	a_k	$P_{obs} \times 10^3$ atmospheres	$P_{cal} \times 10^3$ atmospheres
0.03	1.18×10^{-4}	0.12	0.1204	425	450
0.06	1.62×10^{-5}	0.24	0.24	675	689
0.09	6.03×10^{-6}	0.36	0.36	858	846
0.12	2.34×10^{-6}	0.48	0.48	978	947
0.15	8.32×10^{-7}	0.60	0.60	1075	1025
0.18	3.80×10^{-7}	0.72	0.72	1080	1084
0.21	1.12×10^{-7}	0.84	0.84	1130	1120
0.25	—	1.00	1.00	1180	1181

Fig. 1.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the columns 5 and 6 of the Tables 1-4 that there is fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of osmotic pressure. It will also be noticed that, K decreases as C_{gm} and hence θ decrease, but K_0

remains constant when C_{gm} changes from 0.25 to 0.0625. At $C_{gm} = 0.01$, K_0 decreases appreciably and this fact can be accounted for in the following way. It is to be noted that $K_0 = \frac{K_2}{K_1} \frac{Sdx}{C_{gm}}$ and $x = K'(C_{gm} - C_0)$. Therefore, so long as C_0 is negligibly small compared to C_{gm} , (x/C_{gm}) should remain constant but when C_0 is not negligible compared to C_{gm} , (x/C_{gm}) should decrease as C_{gm} is decreased further. It, therefore, appears that when $C_{gm} = 0.01$, C_0 cannot be neglected any more. It is probable that the sample of PAA (p. 340) used is a mixture containing a low molecular weight polymer which has got solubility C_0 .

It follows from equation (5) that a plot of a_k/P calculated against C_k should be linear. In Fig. I the straight lines II, III and IV and the crosses \times represent the data recorded in the Tables 2 to 4, the values of a_k/P observed being represented by crosses. It will be noticed that the crosses corresponding to a straight line lie quite close to it.

The dissociation constant of PAA (P 340): It has been shown by the author^{4,5} in previous papers that if H_c represents the H^+ ion activity of a sol of a colloidal acid at a concentration C and H_0 the H^+ ion activity of the intermicellar liquid (measured by the potentiometric method) then

$$H_c - H_0 = (a_s - H_0) \theta = a_s \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad (6)$$

where $\theta = \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)}$, C_0 , the c.m.c. or the solubility of the colloidal material, K , a constant and a_s the activity of the H^+ ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the reversible electrode. It may be pointed out that H_0 is always very small compared to a_s and can be neglected.

When C is fairly high, C_0 and H_0 may be neglected compared to C and H_c respectively and equation (6) may be written as follows :

$$H_c = a_s \theta = a_s \frac{C}{K + C} \quad (6a)$$

It is now assumed that a_s is proportional (if not equal) to the effective H^+ ion activity within the diffuse double layer, so that for the exchange of H^+ ions between the fixed Stern-Mukherjee layer and the diffuse double layer the following relation holds good

$$K' a_s (\alpha)^n = K_a (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (7)$$

or

$$a_s = \frac{K_a (1 - \alpha)^n}{K' (\alpha)^n} \quad (7a)$$

where K' is a proportionality constant, K_a the dissociation constant, (α) the bare, i.e., the uncovered fraction of the surface (Stern-Mukherjee layer) per unit area and $(1 - \alpha)$ the fraction of the surface covered by the adsorbed H^+ ions. Since the H^+ ions are bound to the

surface by specific adsorption forces such as hydrogen bonds, besides, the electrovalent linkage, so n has been used in place of unity.

Putting $K_a/K' = K_s$ and substituting $K_s \frac{(1-\alpha)^n}{(\alpha)^n}$ for α_s in equation (6a), we get

$$H_c = \theta K_s \frac{(1-\alpha)^n}{(\alpha)^n} \quad (8)$$

Now K_s which is proportional to K_a may be termed the "surface dissociation constant" of the colloidal acid. Only when the proportionality constant is unity it is identical with K_a .

Using Ostwald's dilution law Briggs⁶ tried to calculate the dissociation constant of arabic acid from measurements of H^+ ion activity at different concentrations of the acid, but found it (the dissociation constant) to vary with dilution. Mitra,⁷ calculated the dissociation constants of some clay acids using Ostwald's dilution law and Henderson's equation, but found no agreement between the two sets of values.

It follows from equation (8) that the quantity these authors have determined is θK_s in which θ varies with dilution.

In order to calculate K_s it is essential not only to find H_c and (α) but also θ . In the case of PAA (P 340) the first two can be found from the data of Kern recorded in the Tables 2-4. Values of θ for PAA (P 340) have also been calculated from the data in the tables II-IV and are recorded in Table 5. The values of pH corresponding to $\log\left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\right) = 0$ have been found by graphical method from the aforesaid data (Tables 2-4).

The data used for the calculation of K_s are summarised in Table 5. In making these calculations it is assumed that the volume is kept constant during the addition³ of NaOH.

TABLE 5
PAA (P 340)

C_{gm}	$(\alpha)/(1-\alpha)$	H_c	θ	pK_s
0.0625	1	7.41×10^{-7}	0.063	4.93
0.125	1	1.42×10^{-6}	0.118	4.95
0.25	1	2.34×10^{-6}	0.212	4.96

From the data recorded above the average value of the "surface dissociation constant" of PAA (P 340) is found to be 1.1×10^{-5} or $pK_s = 4.95$. The value of K_s is thus lower than the dissociation constants of acrylic acid and propionic acid which are 5.6×10^{-5} and 1.3×10^{-5} respectively. This relatively low value of K_s for PAA may be attributed to the combined effect of hydrogen bonding and the proportionality constant K' , being greater than unity. The negative charge on the surface of the colloidal particles will also tend to lower the dissociation constant.

REFERENCES

1. W. Kern, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1938, **A184**, 197.
2. O. Stern, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 508.
3. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920-21, **16**, 103.
4. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 366.
5. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 185.
6. D. R. Briggs, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **38**, 875.
7. R. P. Mitra, *Indian Soc. Soil. Sci. Bull.*, 1942, **4**, 41.
8. W. Kern, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1937-38, **A181**, 249.